

Category	Name	SPIN	Simulink	nuXmv	ProB	AtelierB	UPPAAL	SCADE	FDR4	CPN T.	CADP	mCRL2	SAL	TLA+	UMC
Development Functionalities	Specification/ Modeling	TEXT	GRA	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXT	GRA	GRA	TEXTIN	GRA	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXTIM	TEXT	TEXT
	Code Generation	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Document / Report Generation	PARTIAL	YES	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	YES	PARTIAL	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	NO	NO	PARTIAL
	Requirements Traceability	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Project Management	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Verification Functionalities	Simulation	TEX	GRA	TEX	MIX	NO	GRA	GRA	TEX	GRA	TEX	TEX	TEX	NO	TEX
	Scalability approach	OTF, POR, PAR	BMC	BMC, SYM	SCT	SCT	SMC, SYM	BMC	COM, POR	BMC	COM, PAR	COM	PAR, SCT	SYM, SCT	OTF
	Formal Verification	MC-L	MC-O	MC-L, MC-B	MC-L, MC-B, RF	TP	MC-L, RF	MC-O	RF	MC-B	MC-B, RF	MC-B, RF	MC-L, TP	MC-L, TP	MC-B
	Model-based Testing	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
Language Expressiveness	Nondeterminism	INT	EXT	INT,EXT	INT,EXT	INT,EXT	INT,EXT	EXT	INT,EXT	INT	INT,EXT	INT,EXT	INT,EXT	INT	INT
	Concurrency	ASYNCH	NO	SYNCH	NO	NO	SYNCH	SYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH, SYNCH	ASYNCH	ASYNCH, SYNCH
	Temporal Aspects	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
	Probabilistic or Stochastic	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
	Modularity of the Language	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH
	Supported Data Structures	BASIC	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX	COMPLEX
Tool Flexibility	Float Support	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Backward Compatibility	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	LIKELY	LIKELY	LIKELY	MODERATE	MODERATE	MODERATE
	Standard Input Format	OPEN	PARTIAL	OPEN	OPEN	OPEN	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	OPEN	PARTIAL	STANDARD	OPEN	OPEN	OPEN	STANDARD
	Import/Export	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM
	Modularity of the Tool	LOW	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
Maturity	Team Support	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Industrial Diffusion	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW
Usability	Stage of Development	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	MATURE	PROTO.
	Customer Support	PARTIAL	YES	PARTIAL	YES	YES	YES	YES	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	PARTIAL
	Graphical User Interface	LIMITED	YES	NO	PARTIAL	PARTIAL	YES	YES	LIMITED	PARTIAL	LIMITED	PARTIAL	NO	LIMITED	PARTIAL
	Mathematical Background	MEDIUM	BASIC	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	ADVANCED	MEDIUM	BASIC	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	ADVANCED	MEDIUM
Company Constraints	Quality of Documentation	GOOD	EXCELLENT	GOOD	GOOD	EXCELLENT	GOOD	EXCELLENT	EXCELLENT	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	GOOD	LIMITED
	Cost	FREE	PAY	MIX	FREE	FREE	MIX	PAY	MIX	FREE	MIX	FREE	FREE	FREE	FREE
	Supported Platforms	Windows, Linux,	Windows	Windows, Linux,	Windows	Windows, Linux,									
	Complexity of License	EASY	ADEQUATE	EASY	EASY	EASY	MODERATE	ADEQUATE	MODERATE	EASY	MODERATE	EASY	EASY	EASY	EASY
Railway-specific Criteria	Easy to Install	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	PARTIAL	YES	YES	YES	YES
	CENELEC Certification	NO	PARTIAL	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
	Integration into the CENELEC	MEDIUM	YES	MEDIUM	YES	YES	MEDIUM	YES	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM

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